

Evaluation of Different Insecticides against Fruit Borer (*Helicoverpa armigera*) in Tomatoes Grown in Laghman, Afghanistan

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Abstract:

Tomato fruit borer (*Helicoverpa armigera*) significantly reduces tomato yields in Afghanistan. This study aimed to identify the most effective insecticide for its control in Laghman province, seven treatments were evaluated in randomized complete block design with three replications. These included a control (T1), Lambda-cyhalothrin 2.5% EC (T2), Emamectin Benzoate 1.9% EC (T3), Cypermethrin 10% EC (T4), Deltamethrin 2.5% EC (T5), Chlorpyrifos 40% EC (T6), and Confidor 20% SL (T7). According to our results of the experiment revealed that Emamectin Benzoate (T3) demonstrated the highest efficacy in suppressing tomato fruit borer compared to the control, which had an average of 9.96 larvae per plant, T3

exhibited a significantly lower larval count of 1.63 per plant. Additionally, T3 significantly increased the average number of fruits per plant and achieved the highest total fruit weight (1801.36 g). In terms of infested fruits, T3 recorded the lowest number (1.56) and weight (132.10 g) per plant. Furthermore, the percentage of infested fruits (7.51%) in T3 was remarkably lower than the control's 50.40%, highlighting its strong effectiveness. Our results suggest that Emamectin Benzoate (T3) emerged as the most effective insecticide in preventing tomato fruit borer compared to all other tested treatments.

Keywords: Emamectin Benzoate, fruit borer, *Helicoverpa armigera*, insecticides, tomato.

Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill) belongs to the Solanaceae family, which is the second most significant vegetable crop globally, following potatoes (Kumar *et al.*, 2020). The tomato fruit is consumed in various forms, such as raw, cooked, or processed into a range of products, including soups, pastes, juices, purees, ketchup, and

powders. In addition to its culinary versatility, the tomato holds significant medicinal value, making it a valuable addition to a healthy and balanced diet. It is rich in minerals, vitamins, essential amino acids, sugars, and dietary fibers. Notably, the tomato is abundant in vitamins A, B, and C, as well as iron and phosphorus (Mahla *et al.*, 2017).

Tomato is considered one of the most crucial vegetables cultivated and produced in substantial quantities across various regions of Afghanistan, like Kabul, Kapisa, Parwan, Wardag, Logar, Ghazni, Nangarhar, and Laghman. The total area in the mentioned regions dedicated to tomato cultivation spans 5,436 hectares, resulting in an annual output of 278,454 tons, whereas the estimated overall annual tomato production in Afghanistan is approximately 2,118,500 tons (USAID, 2017). Tomato cultivation and production in Afghanistan lag behind other countries worldwide, indicating a lack of satisfactory results. Various factors hinder the high production of tomatoes in the country. These include low-quality seeds, poor soil conditions, water scarcity, and agricultural pests, all of which contribute to a decrease in tomato yield. Among these challenges, insects pose a significant threat as a major group of agricultural pests, leading to substantial crop losses. Like other crops, tomatoes face numerous challenges, with harmful insects attacking the plants and causing a significant reduction in overall yield.

The tomato fruit borer (*Helicoverpa armigera*), a member of the Noctuidae family within the order Lepidoptera (Babar et al., 2016), is a highly destructive pest that inflicts substantial reductions in both the quantity and quality of tomato crops (Mahla et al., 2017). Estimates suggest that this pest causes damage and destruction amounting to 40-50% of the tomato crop (Pareek & Bhargava, 2003), leading to global economic losses of approximately 5 billion US dollars annually (Sharma, 2001). This polyphagous pest (Babar et al., 2016) has been documented to feed on over 130-180 plant species across 35-49 families (Cunningham & Zalucki, 2014; Tay et al., 2013). Besides tomatoes, it also attacks other vegetable crops like okra, cucumber, maize, sorghum, tobacco, citrus, cotton, soybean, and sunflower (Ahmad et al., 2015; Véték et al., 2017). This pest has the potential to infest vast regions and enlarge its range of attack owing to its high fecundity, flight capacity, and wide host spectrum. The tomato fruit worm (*Helicoverpa armigera*) has a global distribution across Asia, Europe, Africa, and

Australia (Tay et al., 2013). In 2013, an outbreak of this pest occurred in Brazil and subsequently spread to other parts of the American continent from South America (Gonçalves et al., 2019).

Eggs of the tomato fruit borer measure approximately 0.4-0.5 mm in diameter. Nearly spherical with a flattened base, they initially exhibit a glistening yellowish-white color that transitions to dark brown prior to hatching. The larva reaches a length of about 40 mm when fully grown (Hossen, 2008). The larva displays a variable coloration that can include black, brown, green, and yellow hues (Véték et al., 2017).

Damage inflicted by the tomato fruit borer is primarily focused on the larval stage. While younger instars mainly feed on foliage, flower buds, and flowers, resulting in minimal direct fruit damage, later instars undergo a behavioral shift. These later instars bore into developing fruits, making them unsuitable for sale and significantly impacting crop yield and quality (Pareek & Bhargava, 2003; Rasheed et al., 2019). Pupation occurs within the soil at a depth of 3-15 cm. Male pupae initially measure about 23.19 mm in length and 6.23 mm in width, displaying a distinctively rounded front and tapered back. Their initial coloration is light green-yellowish (Mapuranga et al., 2015). The adult stage marks the initial emergence of moths with a body length ranging from 12-20 mm and a wingspan of 30-40 mm. Their coloration varies, but typically, the forewings of females are orange-brown, while males display a lighter greenish-grey hue. A conspicuous black or dark brown kidney-shaped marking near the center of the forewings is present in both sexes. Additionally, the hind wings are characterized by a creamy white color with a dark brown or dark grey band along the outer margin (Véték et al., 2017). The female tomato fruit borer exhibits an ovipositional strategy of laying eggs either singly or in clusters directly upon its host plants. These eggs are preferentially deposited on the upper portions of the plant, including leaves and flowers (Zitsanza & Knight, 2006).

The low tomato yield in Afghanistan can be attributed to several factors, with the tomato

fruit borer (*Helicoverpa armigera*) identified as a significant contributor. This pest directly damages the fruits by piercing and destroying them, resulting in substantial economic losses for farmers. While chemical control using various insecticides is a common approach to pest management, its implementation requires careful consideration.

Arbitrary pesticide use poses significant risks to the environment, including soil contamination, water pollution, and harm to non-target organisms. Moreover, it can't have detrimental effects to human health and lead to contamination of food and animal products. The availability of low-quality pesticides in local markets can further promote overuse and contribute to the negative consequences mentioned above. The objective of this research was to identify effective insecticides for controlling the tomato fruit borer in tomato fields while discouraging the use of ineffective, low-quality insecticides. Furthermore, the findings of this research should be disseminated among farmers, agricultural extension workers, and policymakers to raise awareness about the risks associated with arbitrary pesticide use and to encourage the adoption of safer alternatives.

Materials and Methods

Plant Materials and Growing Conditions

Plant materials used in this study were F1 variety of tomato called MAKKAH. For obtaining seedlings of the mentioned variety, seeds were sown in the Qarghayi district of Laghman province, Afghanistan, according to the methods described by Hossen (2008) with minor changes. One-month-old seedlings were transplanted onto prepared plots at a density of 40 plants per plot with a spacing of 40 cm between plants and 120 cm between plots. Plots were oriented north-south to maximize sunlight exposure. Irrigation was provided as required throughout the growing season. Recommended fertilizers, including compost (10 tons/ha), urea (500 kg/ha), and DAP (200 kg/ha), were applied during land preparation and after planting.

Research Design and Data Analysis

This experiment employed a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with seven treatments and three replications. Each treatment, as detailed in Table 1, was randomly assigned to an experimental plot and applied at the recommended dosage. Following the initial detection of the tomato fruit borer, the same treatment was repeated three times in each plot at seven-day intervals. All applications were conducted in the afternoon with appropriate safety precautions.

Table 1. Information on the Insecticides Employed in the Study

No	Treatment	Insecticide	Formulation	Recommended dose
1	T1	Control	—	—
2	T2	Lambda cyhalothrin	2.5%EC	4ml/liter water
3	T3	Emamectin Benzoate	1.9%EC	4ml/liter water
4	T4	Cypermethrin	10% EC	4ml/liter water
5	T5	Deltamethrin	2.5% EC	3ml/liter water
6	T6	Chlorpyrifos	40 % EC	4ml/liter water
7	T7	Confidor	20% SL	3ml/liter water

Ten plants were randomly selected within each experimental plot for data collection. Data were recorded at four time points: before treatment and during the early, mid, and late fruiting stages. The following observations were recorded at each stage:

- Number of larvae per plant
- Number of fruits per plant
- Total weight of fruits per plant
- Number of infested fruits per plant

- Weight of infested fruits per plant
- Percentage of infested fruits per plant

The percentage of infested fruits per plant was calculated by using the formula:

$$\text{Percentage of infested fruits plant}^{-1} = \frac{\text{Number of the infested fruit plant}^{-1}}{\text{Total number of fruit plant}^{-1}} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

Statistical analysis of the collected data was conducted using SPSS statistical software version 21. A one-way ANOVA was employed to compare the effects of different treatments. Duncan's multiple range test was subsequently conducted at a significance level of $p < 0.05$ to determine significant pairwise differences between treatment groups. GraphPad software was then utilized for data visualization and graphical representation of the results.

Results

Number of Larvae per Plant

Analysis of pre-treatment data revealed no significant difference in the number of larvae per plant across all treatments, including the control. Following the application of the respective treatments, a significant reduction in the number of larvae per plant was observed. The second data collection coincided with the early fruiting stage, as depicted in Figure 1A. The second data collection coincided with the early fruiting stage. The data revealed that the control group (T1) harbored an average of 8.30 larvae per plant, whereas T3, the treatment demonstrating the strongest efficacy, exhibited the lowest larval density with an average of 3.78 larvae per plant. This finding underscores the superior efficacy of treatment T3 in controlling larval populations.

As depicted in Figure 1A, the third survey conducted at the mid-fruiting stage demonstrates the efficacy of all treatments relative to the control. Treatment T3 exhibited the strongest effect, with a mean larval abundance of 2.03 per plant. T2 follows, with a

moderate effect at 3.03 larvae per plant. Notably, even the least effective treatment, T7, with 4.16 larvae per plant, outperformed the control group. The control group exhibited the highest larval abundance, with 9.76 larvae per plant.

The fourth and final data collection occurred at the late-fruiting stage. Similar to the mid-fruiting stage, all treatments demonstrated significant superiority to the control. The control group maintained the highest larval abundance, with 9.96 larvae per plant. Treatment T3 again displayed the strongest effect, with a remarkably low larval abundance of 1.63 per plant. T2 followed closely, with 2.46 larvae per plant. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences among T5 (2.90), T6 (2.96), and T4 (3.06), placing them in the third tier of effectiveness. While T7 (3.43) demonstrated a weaker effect compared to the other treatments, it remained significantly more effective than the control.

Number of Fruits per Plant

As depicted in Figure 1B, the initial data collection before treatment application revealed that the number of fruits per plant ranged from 12.63 to 14.53 across all treatment groups. Following treatment application, the second survey was conducted at the early fruiting stage. Treatments T1 and T7 exhibited lower fruit numbers compared to other groups, with 14.03 and 14.33 fruits per plant, respectively. Conversely, T3 demonstrated the highest early fruit set, with 15.66 fruits per plant, indicating its initial efficacy. The third data collection at the mid-fruiting stage confirmed the effectiveness of all treatments relative to the control. The control group displayed the lowest fruit number, with only 19.9 fruits per plant. In contrast, T3 achieved the highest fruit number of 21.23 fruits per plant, further solidifying its effectiveness. The final survey conducted at the late fruiting stage revealed that treatments T1, T7, T6, T5, and T4 exhibited statistically similar fruit numbers, ranging from 19.70 to 20.10 fruits per plant, with no significant difference from the control. However, T2 and T3 maintained their superior performance, recording 20.43, and 20.76 fruits per plant, respectively, signifying

their continued effectiveness in enhancing fruit production.

Figure 1. (A) The Number of Larvae per Plant is Depicted in the Bar Graphs, which Display the Mean Values of the Variables. (B) Number of Fruits per Plant is Depicted in the Bar Graphs, which Display the Mean Values of the Variables

Total Weight of Fruits per Plant

Before treatment application, the initial survey revealed a range in total fruit weight per plant across treatments, from 1079.86 g in T1 to 1220.03 g in T5 (Figure 2A). At the early fruiting stage, T1 and T7 displayed the lowest total weight with no significant difference (1193.73 g and 1218.30 g, respectively). Treatments T4, T6, T5, T2, and T3 exhibited significantly higher weights, ranging from 1293.00 g to 1331.80 g, demonstrating their early efficacy compared to the control. The mid-fruiting stage survey further highlighted T3's superior performance, with the highest total weight (1804.63 g) significantly exceeding both T1 and T7 (1691.23 g and 1700.36 g, respectively). The final survey at the late fruiting stage again revealed T3's dominance, tied with T2 for the highest total weight (1801.36 g and 1750.83 g), both significantly superior to the control. While T4 (1696.73 g) showed effectiveness, T5 (1666.13 g), T6 (1644.43 g), and T7 (1630.10 g) statistically overlapped with the control (1668.43 g). These findings suggested that, while all treatments enhanced fruit weight compared to the control,

T3 consistently exhibited the strongest effect throughout the fruiting stages.

Number of Infested Fruits per Plant

Examination of Figure 2B reveals that before treatment application, the control group exhibited the lowest number of infested fruits per plant (5.73), while T6 displayed the highest (6.66). Following treatment application, the second data collection at the early fruiting stage demonstrated T3's superior efficacy, with the lowest number of infested fruits per plant (3.90) compared to the control's highest (8.43). The mid-fruiting stage survey further solidified T3's lead, recording the lowest number of infested fruits (2.03) and showcasing its maximum effectiveness. T2 followed closely with the second-best performance (3.20 infested fruits per plant), again highlighting the significant reduction achieved by all treatments compared to the control (10.1 infested fruits per plant). The final survey at the late fruiting stage maintained this trend, with all treatments demonstrating effectiveness relative to the control (9.93 infested fruits per plant). T3 retained its dominance with the lowest infested fruit count

(1.56), followed by T2 (2.43). Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences between T6 (2.93), T5 (3.00), and T4 (3.06), placing them in the third tier of effectiveness. T7 (3.50) demonstrated weaker efficacy but remained

significantly superior to the control. These findings underscore the effectiveness of all treatments in reducing fruit infestation, with T3 consistently proving the most potent throughout the fruiting stages.

Figure 2. (A) Total Weight of Fruits per Plant is Depicted in the Bar Graphs, which Display the Mean Values of the Variables. (B) Number of Infested Fruits per Plant is Depicted in the Bar Graphs, which Display the Mean Values of the Variables. (C) Weight of Infested Fruits per Plant is Depicted in the Bar Graphs, which Display the Mean Values of the Variables

Weight of Infested Fruits per Plant

Figure 2C reveals that pre-treatment data showed a range in weight of infested fruits per plant across treatments, from 485.13 g in T1 to 555.53 g in T3. Subsequent surveys consistently demonstrated the effectiveness of all treatments compared to the control. At the early fruiting stage, T3 emerged as the most effective, with the lowest weight of infested fruits per plant (327.93

g) compared to the control's significantly higher value (711.46 g). The mid-fruiting stage data further solidified T3's lead, with the lowest weight of infested fruits per plant (170.90 g) compared to the control (851.90 g) and all other treatments. T7, with the highest weight (352.90 g), was the least effective among the treatments. At the late fruiting stage, T3 maintained its dominance, recording the lowest weight of infested fruits per plant (132.10 g). T2 followed

closely with the second-best performance (205.47 g). While no significant differences were observed between T6 (246.23 g), T5 (249.20 g), and T4 (256.47 g), all remained significantly superior to the control. Finally, T7 (285.97 g) demonstrated effectiveness, again surpassing the control's significantly higher weight (832.90 g). These findings suggest that while all treatments reduced the weight of infested fruits per plant compared to the control, T3 consistently exhibited the strongest efficacy throughout the fruiting stages.

Percentage of Infested Fruits per Plant (by Number)

Table 2 reveals that before treatment application, the percentage of infested fruits per plant ranged from 45.36% in T1 to 49.61% in T7, with T3 exhibiting the lowest and T7 the highest infestation. Subsequent surveys

consistently demonstrated the effectiveness of all treatments compared to the control. At the early fruiting stage, T3 displayed the strongest effect, reducing infestation to 24.90% compared to the control's significantly higher 60.08%. The trend continued in the mid-fruiting stage, with T3 again recording the lowest infestation (9.56%), while the control remained significantly higher (50.75%). The late fruiting stage data further solidified T3's dominance, exhibiting a remarkably low infestation of 7.51% compared to the control's 50.40%. While all other treatments also showcased effectiveness compared to the control, they trailed T3 considerably, with T2 at 11.89%, T4 at 14.73%, T6 at 14.79%, T5 at 15.05%, and T7 at 17.71%. These findings highlight the consistent efficacy of all treatments in reducing fruit infestation, with T3 demonstrating the most potent effect throughout the fruiting stages.

Table 2. Percentage of Infested Fruits per Plant at Different Stages Related to Different Treatments

Treatments	Before Treatment			Early Fruiting Stage			Mid Fruiting Stage			Late Fruiting Stage		
	TNF	NIF	PIF (%)	TNF	NIF	PIF (%)	TNF	NIF	PIF (%)	TNF	NIF	PIF (%)
T1	12.63	5.73	45.36	14.03	8.43	60.08	19.90	10.10	50.75	19.70	9.93	50.40
T2	13.56	6.36	46.90	15.23	4.23	27.77	20.66	3.20	15.48	20.43	2.43	11.89
T3	14.06	6.60	46.94	15.66	3.90	24.90	21.23	2.03	9.56	20.76	1.56	7.51
T4	14.03	6.50	46.32	15.56	4.50	28.92	20.83	4.06	19.49	20.10	3.03	14.73
T5	14.53	6.63	45.62	15.43	4.16	26.96	20.63	3.76	18.22	19.93	3.00	15.05
T6	14.30	6.66	46.57	15.53	4.50	28.97	20.63	3.56	17.25	19.80	2.93	14.79
T7	13.10	6.50	49.61	14.33	4.83	33.70	20.00	4.16	20.80	19.76	3.50	17.71

Discussion

All evaluated insecticides demonstrated efficacy in suppressing the tomato fruit borer, but Emamectin benzoate exhibited superior larvicidal activity. Larval populations were significantly reduced across all treated plots compared to the control, highlighting the overall effectiveness of the insecticidal interventions. Notably, Emamectin benzoate consistently outperformed other insecticides, aligning with previous research conducted in Italy (Fanigliulo

& Sacchetti, 2008), India (Govindan et al., 2011), and Pakistan (Sattar et al., 2017). These studies similarly reported Emamectin benzoate as the most effective agent in reducing larval abundance or increasing mortality rates, further solidifying its potential as a robust tool for managing this detrimental pest.

Building upon prior research in Peshawar, Pakistan, our findings corroborate the superior efficacy of Emamectin benzoate in controlling tomato fruit borer. Shah et al. (2013)

demonstrated in their 2011 study that plots treated with Emamectin benzoate exhibited the lowest larval counts and fruit infestation rates compared to other insecticides. Similarly, our research aligns with Ahmad et al. (2020), highlighting a significant reduction in both larval abundance and fruit infestation within plots treated with Emamectin benzoate. This consistency across studies reaffirms the superior potential of Emamectin benzoate as a robust control measure for this problematic pest.

Our findings further contribute to the growing body of evidence supporting the superior efficacy of Emamectin benzoate in controlling tomato fruit borer. Javed et al. (2018) demonstrated its effectiveness in Sargodha, Pakistan, where it significantly reduced both larval populations and fruit infestations compared to other synthetic insecticides and botanical extracts. Similarly, Bhavana and Nagar (2019) reported Emamectin benzoate's potent ability to minimize fruit infestation in Uttar Pradesh, India. These findings, consistent with our research, solidify Emamectin benzoate's position as a prominent control agent for this challenging pest.

Conclusion

The statistical analysis of our data revealed that Emamectin benzoate significantly reduced the number of larvae per plant, the number of infested fruits per plant, the weight of infested fruits per plant, and the percentage of infested fruits per plant compared to the control group. Notably, the treatments with Emamectin benzoate also resulted in an increase in the number and weight of total fruits per plant. These findings collectively demonstrate the superior efficacy of Emamectin benzoate in suppressing tomato fruit borer infestation and promoting fruit production compared to other insecticides.

Abbreviation

EC: Emulsifiable Concentrate
SL: Soluble Liquid

TNF: Total number of fruits

NIF: Number of infested fruits

PIF: Percentage of infested fruits

Author Contributions

Mohammad Ikram Azizi and Ahmad Ratib Sharafat conceptualized the research, Mohammad Ikram Azizi conducted the research study and compiled the data. Mohamad Ikram Azizi and Ahmad Ratib Sharafat writing—original draft preparation. Wasiullah Danish helped in the preparation of the design, and helped in the analysis of data. Mohammad Ikram Azizi supervised the research work. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data presented in this study are available upon fair request from the corresponding authors.

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